

The Efficacy of the Legal Mechanisms of the League of Arab States in Settling Regional Crises: The Syrian Crisis as a Case Study

¹ANAS Salih Algdeou, ²Dr. Jassim Zakaria

¹PhD Student in International Law, Faculty of Law, Damascus University

²Professor of International Law, Faculty of Law, Damascus University

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ABSTRACT

This research addresses the role undertaken by the League of Arab States in dealing with the Syrian Crisis from a legal perspective, focusing on the mechanisms for the peaceful settlement of disputes and the extent of their efficacy. The study proceeds from an analysis of the legal framework governing the work of the Arab League, both through its Charter and through the mechanisms developed subsequently. The research also tracks the evolution of the Arab League's positions towards the Syrian Crisis chronologically and analytically; these positions commenced with calls for pacification and internal reforms, before transitioning to the adoption of initiatives aimed at halting violence and launching a national dialogue. At a later stage, the League dispatched field observer missions in an attempt to assess the situation. The research concludes that the efficacy of the Arab League's role remained relatively limited due to several primary reasons, most prominent of which are the absence of legal enforcement mechanisms capable of enforcing its resolutions, as well as the clear divergence in the positions of Member States regarding the Syrian Crisis, and the influence of varying political and strategic considerations on its decisions—a matter which rendered its role closer to a coordinating framework rather than a decisive actor.

Keywords: Arab League, Syrian Crisis, Legal Mechanisms.

INTRODUCTION

The League of Arab States constitutes one of the oldest contemporary regional organisations. Its establishment on the twenty-second of March 1945 coincided with arduous international and Arab circumstances at the end of the Second World War, during which period the majority of Arab States were under the yoke of foreign colonialism. This period was accompanied by the proliferation of liberation movements across the Arab world and the emergence of the concept of pan-Arab nationalism. The inception of the Arab League held paramount significance in the contemporary history of the Arab world, serving as the embodiment of the collective will of the Arab States. The Arab League is distinguished from other organisations in that it unites States situated within a single geographical expanse, inhabited by a single Arab nation possessing a shared history and heritage, common hopes and aspirations, and a similar colonial experience. Throughout the years of its existence, the Arab League has addressed—and continues to address—numerous issues and challenges confronting Arab States on both the domestic and international levels. Consequently, it was imperative to establish legal mechanisms to achieve the paramount objective of the Arab League, namely, the maintenance of Arab security. To this end, the Charter of the Arab League adopted several legal principles and mechanisms for the peaceful settlement of crises. Within the limits of the competences and powers vested in it under its Charter, the Arab League has sought to resolve all conflicts confronting it. At times, its efforts have been crowned with success, while at others, achieving a resolution has proven elusive, whether due to reasons pertaining to the dispute settlement system adopted by the League, or due

to factors created by the parties to the conflict or by external actors. In performing its role in crisis resolution, the Arab League relies on the legal provisions enshrined in its Charter, as well as on the resolutions of the Arab Summit and the various Councils of the League.

The Syrian case constitutes a prominent model for testing the efficacy of these mechanisms, as the Arab League confronted complex challenges in managing the developments of the Syrian crisis, a matter which revealed the limits of its capacity to influence the course of the conflict in light of the intertwining of domestic factors and regional and international interventions.

RESEARCH PROBLEM:

The research problem centres on the following question: to what extent has the League of Arab States, through the mechanisms prescribed in its charters, been able to find successful and effective solutions for the settlement of conflicts confronting it and confronting Member States, particularly Syria?

The following sub-questions branch out from the main question of this research:

1. What are the legal mechanisms upon which the Charter of the League of Arab States relies for the peaceful settlement of crises?
2. How did the League of Arab States deal with the developments of the Syrian crisis, and what are the most prominent tools it utilised in doing so?
3. How can the role played by the League of Arab States in settling the crisis in Syria be assessed?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH:

The significance of the research arises from the fact that it provides an analysis of the role of the League of Arab States in the peaceful settlement of crises, by identifying the legal mechanisms adopted within the Arab League for crisis resolution and assessing the efficacy of these mechanisms, with a focus on the Syrian case as a practical example. This is particularly relevant as the current Arab reality witnesses numerous challenges that have, in turn, led to the fracturing of regional Arab security, thereby underscoring the reliance upon the Arab League as a regional organisation and the importance of its role in consolidating collective security.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH:

The research aims to achieve the following:

1. To identify the legal framework governing the operation of the League of Arab States within the context of the peaceful settlement of crises, applying this to the Syrian case.
2. To demonstrate the efficacy of the legal system adopted by the Arab League in peaceful settlement when addressing the Syrian conflict.
3. To assess the role of the Arab League in peaceful settlement and to highlight the areas of success and failure.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Given the nature of the research, the researcher deems it essential to rely on several complementary methodologies to obtain the necessary information to address the research problem, namely:

The Descriptive Methodology: through reviewing the legal system adopted within the policy of the Arab League, including the peaceful means and diplomatic strategies employed in the conflicts it has confronted.

The Analytical Methodology: for the purpose of assessing and analysing the role performed by the Arab League within the context of the Syrian crisis.

RESEARCH PLAN:

Section I: Legal Mechanisms for Crisis Settlement within the Framework of the League of Arab States.

- Sub-section I: Mechanisms Provided for in the Charter and the Work of the Arab League.
- Sub-section II: Mechanisms Provided for in the Documents Annexed to the Charter.

Section II: The Applied Framework of the Role of the League of Arab States in the Syrian Crisis.

- Sub-section I: The Position of the Arab League on the Outbreak of the Syrian Crisis.
- Sub-section II: Mechanisms of the Arab League's Intervention in the Syrian Crisis.
- Sub-section III: Assessment of the Role of the Arab League in the Syrian Crisis.

SECTION I: LEGAL MECHANISMS FOR CRISIS SETTLEMENT WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE LEAGUE OF ARAB STATES

The principle of the peaceful settlement of crises and the non-use of force or the threat thereof has become an established matter in international law jurisprudence and one of the fundamental, deep-rooted principles governing international relations; indeed, this principle has ascended to the status of *jus cogens* (peremptory norms).¹ The League of Arab States, as a regional organisation possessing a specific set of competences, has placed an obligation upon Member States prohibiting the use of force, mandating respect for the sovereignty of States, and requiring the settlement of any dispute by peaceful means. To this end, the League has established a set of methods and mechanisms to be resorted to for peaceful settlement.²

Accordingly, the study in this section is divided into two sub-sections: Mechanisms Provided for in the Charter and the Work of the Arab League (Sub-section I), and Mechanisms Provided for in the Documents Annexed to the Charter (Sub-section II).

SUB-SECTION I: MECHANISMS PROVIDED FOR IN THE CHARTER AND THE WORK OF THE ARAB LEAGUE

Article 5 of the Charter of the Arab League addressed the issue of crisis resolution and the means for their peaceful settlement. This article was more modest than the text of Article 33 of the Charter of the United Nations, which addresses the issue of the peaceful settlement of disputes.³ Article 5 was confined to mentioning only two methods for crisis settlement, namely: mediation and arbitration, whilst noting that the League has introduced other peaceful means through its work for crisis resolution.

FIRST: THE ADOPTED PEACEFUL MEANS

The Charter of the Arab League was confined to mentioning a single diplomatic method enabling the latter's intervention in the peaceful settlement of crises, namely mediation. Mediation is defined as the effort of a third party to find a settlement to an existing dispute between conflicting parties by presenting proposals aimed at reconciling their views. Mediation may occur either at the request of the parties to the dispute, on the initiative of this third party, or on the initiative of an international organisation (global or regional)⁴; it is a method characterised by being optional, amicable, voluntary, and non-binding.⁵

The Council of the League is customarily entrusted with exerting its efforts in mediation between the parties to the dispute to achieve the required settlement, by participating in the

¹ Al-Majzoub, Mohammad. (2007). *Public International Law*. 6th ed. Beirut: Lebanon. Halabi Legal Publications. pp. 789–790

² The League of Arab States was formed in Cairo on 22 March 1945 pursuant to the Alexandria Protocol of 1944, which called for the establishment of an Arab organisation to bind Arabs to one another. The League was founded by 6 members, namely (Egypt, Syria, Jordan, Iraq, Saudi Arabia, and Lebanon). Currently, the Arab League comprises 22 members, and its primary objective is to strengthen relations among Member States in order to safeguard their independence and sovereignty. For more, see the official website of the League of Arab States, available at the following link: <http://www.leagueofarabstates.net/>. Accessed: 25 May 2026.

³ Article 33 stipulates that: 1. "The parties to any dispute, the continuance of which is likely to endanger the maintenance of international peace and security, shall, first of all, seek a solution by negotiation, enquiry, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, judicial settlement, resort to regional agencies or arrangements, or other peaceful means of their own choice."

⁴ The mediator may be a prominent diplomatic figure possessing amicable relations with the conflicting parties, or a representative of an international organisation, such as: Kofi Annan, Lakhdar Brahimi, and Ban Ki-moon. The mediator may also be a Head of State or Government.

⁵ United Nations. (1992). *Handbook on the Peaceful Settlement of Disputes between States*. United Nations Publication. New York: USA. pp. 40–41.

investigation of the causes and nature of the dispute. The Council of the Arab League constitutes the sole body authorised to undertake mediation.⁶

Through researching practical practices, the Arab League has expanded the scope of its practice of mediation; the League did not restrict its practice of mediation solely to conflicts where war was feared, but extended it to encompass the majority of Arab conflicts across their various stages and degrees of gravity.⁷

It is worth noting that mediation procedures, in general, are not governed by a specific timeframe, as there is no legal provision regulating this matter. It may be prolonged or shortened depending on the nature and complexity of the crisis. Mediation terminates either upon the resolution of the crisis, or when one of the parties rejects the mediation or the mediator.⁸

By reference to Article 5 of the Charter of the Arab League, we find a clear indication of the existence of a judicial method alongside mediation as a means for crisis settlement; this method is represented by arbitration.

The most important definition of arbitration is that determined by the 1907 Hague Convention for the Pacific Settlement of International Disputes,⁹ where it was stated in this Convention that: "International arbitration has for its object the settlement of disputes between States by Judges of their own choice and on the basis of respect for law. Recourse to arbitration implies an engagement to submit in good faith to the Award."¹⁰

Article 5 of the Charter of the Arab League confirms in its general context that arbitration is optional and not mandatory; the matter remains contingent upon the desire and will of the conflicting parties. Consequently, the Council of the Arab League has no right to undertake arbitration functions without the consent of the parties concerned in the dispute, regardless of the degree of gravity or nature of this dispute. The Council of the League must adjudicate the dispute by a resolution issued by a majority vote, whether in the case of mediation or arbitration.¹¹

SECOND: THE INTRODUCED PEACEFUL MEANS

The Arab League was not content with the methods provided for in its Charter to confront the issues and challenges facing it and facing Member States, but rather introduced several practical methods in accordance with the variables within the League's environment.

Good Offices: This encompasses any amicable activity undertaken by a third party—whether a State, an organisation, or a prominent diplomatic figure—either on its own initiative or at the request of one of the parties to the dispute, with the aim of creating the best possible means for initiating or resuming negotiations.¹²

⁶ Article 5(3) of the Charter of the League of Arab States stipulates that: "The Council shall mediate in a dispute which may lead to war between two member States or between a Member State and another State in order to conciliate them."

⁷ Among the most prominent crises in which the Council of the Arab League intervened by forming mediation committees are: the West Bank crisis in Palestine in 1950, and the Moroccan-Algerian crisis in 1963.

⁸ Examples of the rejection of mediation in the Arab world include: the Moroccan Government's rejection of the United Arab Republic's mediation in 1963 to end the Moroccan-Algerian crisis over the border areas between the two countries (Tindouf and Béchar), which led to the outbreak of a military confrontation between the two countries known as the "Sand War" and continued until 1972. See: Abdel Hamid, Aisha. (2020). The Problem of the Historical Algerian-Moroccan Border Dispute. Academic Journal for Research and Scientific Publishing. Issue 12. pp. 1–10. El Tarf: Algeria. Chadli Bendjedid University. p. 5.

⁹ Adopted at the Peace Conference held in the city of The Hague, Netherlands, on 18 October 1907.

¹⁰ The text of Article 37 of the 1907 Hague International Convention.

¹¹ Article 5(4) stipulates that: "The awards of arbitration and the decisions for mediation shall be taken by a majority vote."

¹² Mohammad, Ali. (2017). Objectives and Means of Diplomacy in Settling International Disputes. Journal of International Studies. Issue 68. pp. 125–148. Baghdad: Iraq. University of Baghdad. p. 141.

The party performing good offices works to reconcile the views of the two parties to the dispute and to mitigate tension between them, in order to create the conditions for reaching direct negotiations or resuming them in the event of their cessation, without participating in the negotiations directly. This party is not entitled to present proposals or solutions to settle the dispute, as its mission is confined to rendering advice and providing channels of communication between the conflicting parties. Good offices do not possess any binding force, as they constitute optional, amicable endeavours.¹³

The Arab League has relied upon good offices within its scope of work despite the absence of any provision for them in the Charter of the League. Among the most prominent cases in which the League exerted its good offices was the Iraqi–Kuwaiti dispute in 1961 regarding the borders and the issue of Iraq's annexation of Kuwait.¹⁴ The Secretary-General of the League, Mohamed Abdel Khalek Hassouna, exerted his good offices with the aim of preventing the escalation of the dispute, and his endeavours succeeded in doing so.

Conciliation Commissions: This is a method through which an existing dispute is referred to a specific commission for the purpose of examining all aspects of the dispute and proposing a solution to the parties concerned therewith. These commissions are often composed of an uneven number of members. The matter of proposals remains non-binding, as both parties retain full discretion to accept or reject the commission's proposals.¹⁵

The Council of the Arab League has formed numerous conciliation commissions to consider certain crises, among which we mention the Conciliation Commission on the Yemen War in 1954 to conciliate between the conflicting parties, as well as the Conciliation Commission on the Battle of the Tunisian Bizerte Base in 1961 between France and Tunisia.¹⁶

Enquiry: This is the method that seeks to study the causes of a conflict at close proximity in an attempt to find a solution suitable for the conflicting parties in an impartial manner. It takes the form of a commission concerned with understanding the circumstances of the facts of the dispute by proceeding to the site of the dispute and reaching a solution with complete integrity and impartiality.¹⁷

The primary purpose of an enquiry is to determine the material facts and the points of disagreement between the conflicting parties, leaving it to them to draw the conclusions arising therefrom, either directly by means of negotiations or indirectly by means of arbitration.¹⁸

Enquiry was present within the scope of the Arab League on the practical level, as the League resorted to forming numerous enquiry commissions in several cases, among which we mention the British–Yemeni dispute over the Yemeni protectorates in 1946, where the Council of the League decided to form a fact-finding commission.

SUB-SECTION II: MECHANISMS PROVIDED FOR IN THE DOCUMENTS ANNEXED TO THE CHARTER

Within the framework of keeping pace with international and Arab situations and developments, other mechanisms for dispute settlement were added within the framework of

¹³ Herein lies the difference between mediation and good offices: the party undertaking good offices contents itself with reconciling views and urging the parties to negotiate without participating directly therein, whereas the party undertaking mediation participates in the negotiations directly and is capable of presenting proposals and adopting decisions. See: Al-Majzoub, Mohammad. (2007). Op. cit. p. 797.

¹⁴ Taher, Qahtan. (2014). History of the Iraqi-Kuwaiti Conflict. Journal of the College of Basic Education for Educational and Human Sciences. Issue 18. pp. 499–507. Babylon: Iraq. University of Babylon. p. 505.

¹⁵ United Nations. (1992). Op. cit. p. 55.

¹⁶ Al-Otaibi, Ghalib. (2010). The League of Arab States and the Settlement of Arab Disputes. 1st ed. Riyadh: Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Naif Arab University for Security Sciences Publications. p. 46 et seq.

¹⁷ Afftan, Omar. (2020). The Peaceful Settlement of International Disputes. Journal of Legal and Political Sciences. Special Issue. pp. 269–296. Baqubah: Iraq. Diyala University. p. 276.

¹⁸ Touri, Yakhliif. (2018). The Settlement of International Disputes by Peaceful Means. Al-Ijtihad Journal for Legal and Economic Studies. Vol. 7. Issue 2. pp. 289–311. Tamanghasset: Algeria. University of Tamanghasset. p. 294.

the Arab League, through adding a set of annexes to the Charter of the Arab League. These additions were necessary, particularly in light of the emergence of new regional organisations seeking a position and a role on the Arab regional arena,¹⁹ and in order to transcend existing differences among Arab States regarding certain matters, "such as the amendment of the Charter of the Arab League".

FIRST: THE JOINT DEFENCE AND ECONOMIC COOPERATION TREATY

Following the expiration of five years from the establishment of the Arab League, the Council of the League approved the conclusion of the Joint Defence and Economic Cooperation Treaty, which was signed by the Member States on 17 June 1950,²⁰ with a view to remedying the deficiencies that marred the Charter of the Arab League in the defensive and economic fields. The Treaty incorporated provisions confirming the contracting States' commitment to continuous peace and security, and their determination to resolve all crises among Member States by peaceful means, whether in their mutual relations or in their relations with other States.²¹ It also included provisions pertaining to confronting armed aggression, whereby an aggression committed against one or more of the Member States is deemed an attack against all contracting States, and it mandated an obligation upon Member States to assist the attacked State or States in accordance with the principle of legitimate self-defence.²²

The Joint Defence Treaty constitutes a significant achievement for the Arab League, particularly when considering the outcomes resulting from its conclusion, represented by the establishment of a Unified Military Command comprising representatives of the General Staff of the armies of the contracting States to organise joint defence plans,²³ in addition to the formation of a Joint Defence Council comprising the Ministers of Foreign Affairs and Defence of the contracting States to implement matters relating to confronting any armed aggression against Member States.²⁴

SECOND: THE ARAB PEACE AND SECURITY COUNCIL

Following the establishment of the Arab League in 1945, the number of Arab States joining it increased, and their problems multiplied and diversified. The majority of these problems arose because the Charter of the League focused on national causes and failed to establish mechanisms for settling crises among Arab States. Consequently, Arab leaders began contemplating the establishment of an operational mechanism based on proactive action to identify crisis hotspots prior to their emergence and to work on preventing them before conflicts intensify, as well as creating a new institution tasked with following up on Arab disputes and presenting them before Arab Summit conferences to enable them to adopt the necessary means to settle them; this institution was designated as the Arab Peace and Security Council.²⁵

The Arab Peace and Security Council was established in 2006 pursuant to Arab Summit Conference Resolution No. 331 in Khartoum, and its Statute was adopted by the Council of the Arab League under Resolution No. 6856 in 2008. The objectives of the Council are to prevent conflicts that may arise among Arab States, and to manage and settle them in the event of their

¹⁹ An example of such regional organisations is the African Union: an organisation comprising 55 states in Africa, established in 2002 in South Africa. The objective of the organisation lies in uniting ranks among African states and resolving common challenges through collective action. For more, see the official website of the African Union, available at the following link: <https://au.int/ar/>. Accessed: 25 May 2026.

²⁰ The Joint Defence and Economic Cooperation Treaty between the States of the League of Arab States, 1950.

²¹ Article 1, op. cit.

²² Article 2, op. cit.

²³ Article 5, op. cit.

²⁴ Article 6, op. cit.

²⁵ Al-Fatlawi, Suhail. (2011). *The League of Arab States in Facing the Challenges of Globalisation, Part II: The Organs of the League*. 1st ed. Amman: Jordan. Dar Al-Hamid for Publishing and Distribution. pp. 167–168.

occurrence, in addition to monitoring, studying, and submitting recommendations to the Council of the Arab League regarding developments affecting Arab national security.²⁶

Pursuant to the Charter of the Arab League, the Arab Peace and Security Council is entrusted with a set of mandates, among which we mention the following: preparing strategies for the maintenance of Arab peace and security; enhancing Arab capabilities in the field of preventive action by exerting diplomatic endeavours, including mediation, reconciliation, and conciliation, and removing the causes of tension to prevent any future conflicts; in addition to supporting post-war reconstruction efforts to preclude their renewal.²⁷

The Arab Peace and Security Council does not possess the authority to issue binding resolutions independently of the Council of the Arab League; hence, all submissions made by this Council constitute nothing more than non-binding recommendations.²⁸

We conclude from the foregoing that the Charter of the Arab League did not expand upon the prescribed methods for the peaceful settlement of crises, which prompted it to rely on other methods in accordance with the variables and circumstances surrounding the League. This stands in contrast to the Charter of the United Nations, which clearly set out the methods of crisis settlement in a written text. On the whole, it can also be said that the mechanisms of the Arab League all coalesce into a single mould, represented by the settlement of disputes through peaceful means, the strengthening of bonds among Arab States, and respect for the principles and rules of international law.

SECTION II: THE APPLIED FRAMEWORK OF THE ROLE OF THE LEAGUE OF ARAB STATES IN THE SYRIAN CRISIS

With the outbreak of the Syrian Crisis, the League of Arab States confronted a true test of its capacity to address the internal conflicts of Member States by peaceful and legal means, which posed a major challenge to its institutional and political capabilities. The League was compelled to balance its role between respecting the sovereignty of Member States and intervening to halt the escalation and protect regional security and stability. During this period, the League adopted clear positions on the ongoing events and issued a series of resolutions and statements aimed at mitigating the impact of the conflict. It also attempted to activate multiple intervention mechanisms that encompassed political mediation, diplomatic pressure, and monitoring the situation on the ground via inspection missions.

Accordingly, the study in this section is divided into three sub-sections: The Position of the Arab League on the Outbreak of the Syrian Crisis (Sub-section I), Mechanisms of the Arab League's Intervention in the Syrian Crisis (Sub-section II), and Assessment of the Role of the Arab League in the Syrian Crisis (Sub-section III).

SUB-SECTION I: THE POSITION OF THE ARAB LEAGUE ON THE OUTBREAK OF THE SYRIAN CRISIS

The position of the League of Arab States since the initial stages of the outbreak of the movement in Syria was characterised by caution and a gradual approach in dealing with the events, as it was keen to adopt an approach marked by political prudence and the avoidance of direct involvement in internal Syrian affairs. At this stage, the League focused on monitoring the developments of the situation on the ground and observing the nature of the interaction between the authority and the demonstrators, whilst emphasizing the necessity of containing the situation within the national framework. In this context, it called for self-restraint and the avoidance of the use of violence, stressing the importance of the Syrian Government

²⁶ Article 2 of the Statute of the Arab Peace and Security Council, 2008.

²⁷ Article 6, *op. cit.*

²⁸ Al-Fatlawi, Suhail. (2011). *Op. cit.* p. 195.

responding to popular demands through the adoption of a package of political and economic reforms that would absorb the state of popular congestion and maintain internal stability.²⁹

In its approach to the Syrian Crisis, the Arab League relied on a set of constants and principles that formed the governing framework for its positions. It repeatedly affirmed the necessity of preserving the unity of the Syrian State and its territorial integrity, considering this a fundamental pillar of regional stability. It also stressed its rejection of slipping into chaos or armed conflict, due to the grave repercussions this would entail for Arab security as a whole. Concurrently, the League sought to achieve a delicate balance between respecting the principle of national sovereignty and non-interference in the internal affairs of States, and supporting the aspirations of the Syrian people for freedom, dignity, and political reform. Furthermore, it paid increasing attention to the humanitarian dimension, by emphasizing the need to protect civilians and work towards mitigating their suffering in light of the escalating violence.³⁰

With the evolution and acceleration of events, and the widening scope of protests to encompass multiple regions of the country, the position of the Arab League began to undergo a gradual shift towards greater clarity in expressing concern over the situation on the ground. The League demonstrated an increasing level of preoccupation with the repercussions of the continued use of force against demonstrators, considering that this approach would complicate the scene. Within this framework, it expressed its rejection of the escalation of violence and called for its immediate cessation, whilst emphasizing the importance of resorting to dialogue as the sole option to overcome the crisis. The League also affirmed the necessity of launching a comprehensive national dialogue process that includes the various components of Syrian society, without exclusion, with the aim of reaching a consensual formula leading to a peaceful political settlement. These calls reflected a growing realisation within the League that a security solution is insufficient to address the root causes of the events, and that an actual response to popular demands represents an essential entry point for achieving stability.

Thus, it can be said that the position of the Arab League at this stage was characterised by an attempt to contain the situation through political and diplomatic tools based on pacification and the call for reform and dialogue, without transitioning as yet to the adoption of executive measures or practical initiatives.

SUB-SECTION II: MECHANISMS OF THE ARAB LEAGUE'S INTERVENTION IN THE SYRIAN CRISIS

With the continued lack of responsiveness from the Syrian regime and the escalating pace of violence, the Council of the League of Arab States convened an extraordinary meeting at the level of Foreign Ministers to discuss developments in Syria at that time. The meeting concluded with the adoption of the (First Arab Initiative on Syria), issued on 28 August 2011, with the aim of actively contributing to finding a national exit and limiting the repercussions of its exacerbation on the country's stability. This was in addition to seeking to spare Syrian bloodshed, preventing the country from slipping into further violence and chaos, and affirming the rejection of any form of foreign intervention—whether direct or indirect—that undermines national sovereignty. The Initiative comprised thirteen clauses, the most important of which can be highlighted as follows:³¹

²⁹ Abdel Karim, Imad Omar Mohammad. (2018). *The Role of the League of Arab States in Resolving Arab Issues 2011–2017*. Master's Thesis. Department of Political Science. Faculty of Arts and Sciences. Middle East University. Amman: Jordan. p. 105 et seq.

³⁰ Shamran, Ammar. (2020). *The Role of the League of Arab States in Managing the Syrian Crisis in Light of the Arab Spring Revolutions (2011–2018)*. Scientific Journal of the Faculty of Economic Studies and Political Science. Vol. 5. Issue 9. pp. 189–226. Alexandria: Egypt. Alexandria University. p. 196.

³¹ Research Department. (2024). *Is the Arab League Capable of Saving Syria*. Research published by the Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies. Doha: Qatar. Available at the following link: https://www.dohainstitute.org/ar/PoliticalStudies/Pages/Is_the_Arab_League_capable_of_saving_Syria.aspx. Accessed: 25 May 2026.

- The release of all detainees, and the provision of redress for all forms of harm suffered by citizens.
- The immediate cessation of all acts of violence against civilians, and the withdrawal of all military presence from Syrian cities to spare Syrian bloodshed.
- The declaration of clear and specific principles by the President, outlining reform steps.
- The formation of a coalition government of national unity, headed by a prime minister acceptable to the opposition forces engaged in the dialogue process, to work with the President, with its mandate defined as conducting transparent parliamentary elections that are pluralistic on both party and individual levels.
- The holding of pluralistic presidential elections open to all candidates in 2014 (the date of the end of Bashar al-Assad's term at that time).
- The League of Arab States, upon invitation by the President, playing a facilitating and encouraging role for dialogue, in accordance with a mechanism to be agreed upon.

The League of Arab States attempted to find executive mechanisms to put the Initiative into practice; accordingly, it formed an Arab Ministerial Committee chaired by the Foreign Minister of Qatar, with the membership of the Foreign Ministers of Algeria, Sudan, the Sultanate of Oman, and Egypt, along with the Secretary-General of the League of Arab States (Nabil Elaraby). The mandate of this Committee was to contact the Syrian leadership to halt acts of violence, remove military presence, initiate dialogue between the Syrian Government and opposition parties, and implement reforms.³²

The Syrian regime at the time expressed reservations about the resolution (under the pretext of assigning the chairmanship of the Ministerial Committee to the State of Qatar). However, it was compelled to engage with the Arab efforts as a result of the Arab, regional, and international consensus on the Arab League's initiative and its role in resolving the Syrian crisis. Consequently, an initial action plan was reached to implement the Arab Initiative, but it was not executed on the ground, which prompted the Council of the Arab League to suspend Syria's membership in the League and to impose economic sanctions upon it.³³

Nevertheless, the Arab League did not close the door to a political solution, and decided, by the end of 2011, to grant the Syrian regime another opportunity to implement the Arab solution by dispatching an Arab monitoring mission to Syria (headed by the Sudanese General Mohamed Al-Dabi) to ascertain the implementation of the Arab solution. The observer mission entered Syria at the beginning of January 2012 and withdrew approximately two weeks after commencing its work, as a result of the continuation of violence and infighting, and the regime's non-compliance with the terms of the Arab action plan. Following the failure of the observer mission to achieve its objectives, the Council of Arab Foreign Ministers convened on 22 January 2012 and approved the (Second Arab Initiative), which comprised six points, the most prominent of which we mention:³⁴

- The formation of a government of national unity within two months, in which the authority and the opposition participate, headed by an agreed-upon figure, whose mandate shall be to

³² Küçükkeleş, Müjge. (2012). Arab League's Syrian Policy. Foundation for Political, Economic and Social Research (SETA) Publications. Ankara: Turkey. p. 6.

³³ Syria's membership was suspended on 12 November 2011 pursuant to Resolution No. 7438, and the decision was adopted with the approval of 18 states, whereas Lebanon and Yemen objected to the resolution, and Iraq abstained from voting. The economic sanctions were imposed pursuant to Resolution No. 7442 of 2011, which included suspending financial transactions with the Central Bank of Syria, freezing the financial assets of the Syrian Government, and halting commercial exchanges and project funding.

³⁴ Research Department. (2012). Syria and the New Arab Initiative. Research published by Al Jazeera Centre for Studies. Doha: Qatar. Available at the following link: <https://studies.aljazeera.net/ar/article/447>. Accessed: 25 May 2026.

implement the terms of the Arab League's plan and to prepare for free, pluralistic parliamentary and presidential elections under Arab and international supervision.

- The delegation of full powers by the President of the Republic to his First Vice-President to cooperate with the government of national unity to enable it to perform its duties during the transitional phase.
- The declaration by the government of national unity, immediately upon its formation, that its objective is to establish a pluralistic democratic system in which citizens are equal regardless of their affiliations and sects, and in which power is rotated peacefully.

The Initiative included instructing the Secretary-General of the League of Arab States to appoint a special envoy to follow up on the political process. The regime rejected this Initiative, describing it as a blatant interference in the internal affairs of Syria, a violation of its national sovereignty, and a flagrant breach of the objectives for which the Arab League was established, as well as of Article 8 of the League's Charter.³⁵

Meanwhile, the (Syrian National Council), representing the external opposition, expressed its support for the Initiative, considering it an appropriate exit, provided there was full responsiveness from the regime. However, this Initiative also failed to see the light of day, which prompted the Arab League to announce the failure of the Arab solution and to transfer the Syrian file to the United Nations.³⁶

The League consistently affirmed, in numerous resolutions and statements, the necessity of halting violence, allowing the entry of aid, and achieving national reconciliation.³⁷

Years into the Syrian crisis, with all its various developments, the Arab League and the Arab track returned to the scene. The earthquake that struck Syria in 2023 formed a turning point in shifting the Arab League's policy towards Syria, as the Arab League decided on 7 May 2023 that Syria would resume occupying its seat in the League. It launched its latest initiative, known as the ("step-for-step") policy, which meant that the Syrian regime must take specific steps on the ground towards a political solution to the crisis, in return for the Arab League taking reciprocal steps to restore full relations with Syria. The initiative achieved limited success by breaking the political Arab isolation that had been imposed on Syria, but it did not make real progress in the political solution,³⁸ and the initiative continued until the fall of the regime on 8 December 2024.

Following the fall of the defunct regime, the role of the League of Arab States emerged anew within the context of dealing with the transitional phase. It sought to reposition itself as a regional actor supporting stability and the reconstruction of the Syrian State. Its movements at this stage focused on supporting a transitional political track aimed at reshaping state institutions on consensual foundations, whilst emphasizing respect for Syria's unity and sovereignty and preventing a slide into chaos or partition. The League also worked on revitalising Arab–Arab coordination to provide humanitarian and economic support, contribute to reconstruction efforts, and support the return of refugees.

SUB-SECTION III: ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF THE ARAB LEAGUE IN THE SYRIAN CRISIS

³⁵ Article 8 of the Charter of the Arab League stipulates that: "Every Member State of the League shall respect the form of government obtaining in the other States of the League, and shall recognize the form of government obtaining as one of the rights of those States, and shall pledge itself not to take any action tending to change that form."

³⁶ Subsequent to this, the joint envoy Kofi Annan was appointed, followed by the envoy Lakhdar Brahimi.

³⁷ Such as Arab League Resolution No. 7460 dated 10 March 2012, the Kuwait Summit Statement dated 25 March 2014, and the Saudi Arabia Summit Statement dated 15 April 2018.

³⁸ Assi, Abdul Wahab. (2023). Arab Policies Towards the Syrian Regime: Motives and Outcomes. Research published by Al Jazeera Centre for Studies. Doha: Qatar. Available at the following link: <https://studies.aljazeera.net/ar/article/5664>. Accessed: 25 May 2026.

The role of the League of Arab States in addressing the Syrian crisis can be assessed by analysing the entirety of its movements and positions during the various stages through which Syria passed. This is achieved by identifying the most prominent successes it attained, balanced against the failures that limited its efficacy and affected the outcomes of its intervention.

FIRST: SUCCESSES

The Arab League achieved a number of relative successes in its management of the Syrian file, represented by its capacity to break the political stalemate in the early stages of the Crisis. This was done by placing the Syrian context on the agenda of joint Arab action and transforming it into a high-priority regional issue. It also succeeded in formulating a collective Arab position—albeit relatively—towards the developments of the situation in Syria, which manifested in the issuance of political initiatives and action plans aimed at containing the situation.

The League sought to activate the tools of diplomatic action by launching the first and second Arab initiatives, forming ministerial committees, dispatching an Arab observer mission, and appointing a joint envoy. This reflected a serious attempt to utilise peaceful mechanisms to address the conflict. Furthermore, these movements contributed to shedding light on the humanitarian conditions in Syria and enhancing international attention to the conflict.³⁹

Additionally, the League played an important role in transferring the Syrian file to the international level through coordination with the United Nations, a matter which contributed to the internationalisation of the Syrian issue and its inclusion among the priorities of the international community. At a later stage, Syria's return to its seat in the League in 2023 represented a step towards breaking the Arab political isolation and opening new channels of communication, thereby reflecting an attempt to reactivate the Arab role in managing the Syrian file.⁴⁰

Following the fall of the regime, the League's contribution emerged in supporting the transitional phase by affirming the unity of Syria, supporting the political track, and attempting to coordinate Arab efforts in the fields of relief and reconstruction, which reflects its continuous presence as an overarching regional framework.

SECOND: FAILURES

Notwithstanding these efforts, the Arab League confronted clear failures that limited the efficacy of its role in the Syrian crisis. The Arab initiatives, both the first and the second, failed to achieve their primary objectives as a result of the Syrian regime's non-compliance with their terms and the absence of real enforcement mechanisms for their implementation. Moreover, the Arab observer mission was unable to perform its mandates as required and withdrew prematurely, reflecting the limited executive capacity of the League on the ground.

The issue of divisions among Member States also emerged, which adversely affected the unity of the Arab position and weakened the League's capacity to adopt decisive and effective resolutions. Furthermore, the League suffered from the limitation of its political and economic leverage and its lack of executive means capable of enforcing its resolutions, rendering its role in many instances closer to a symbolic character.⁴¹

Among the aspects of failure was also the delay in adopting more firm positions in the initial stages of the crisis, a matter which allowed the situation to exacerbate and become more

³⁹ Alexander, Kristian, Serhal, Gina Bou. (2023). Return to the Arab League: How Syria's Readmission Affects Regional Stability. Orion Policy Institute Publications. Washington: USA. Available at: <https://orionpolicy.org/return-to-the-arab-league-how-syrias-readmission-affects-regional-stability/>. Accessed: 25 May 2026.

⁴⁰ Research Department. (2023). The Background of Syria's Return to the Arab League and its Regional Repercussions. Research published by Al Jazeera Centre for Studies. Doha: Qatar. Available at the following link: <https://studies.aljazeera.net/ar/article/5652>. Accessed: 25 May 2026.

⁴¹ Baqas, Khaled. (2019). The Impact of Arab Political Transformations After 2011 on the Reality and Future of Arab Integration Institutions. Journal of Legal and Political Sciences. Vol. 10. Issue 1. pp. 1218–1229. Djelfa: Algeria. Ziane Achour University. p. 1225.

complex. Additionally, transferring the file to the United Nations constituted an implicit admission of the League's incapacity to manage the crisis independently.

With regard to the subsequent stages, the "step-for-step" initiative did not achieve tangible progress in the course of the political solution; its impact was confined to restoring political communication without bringing about a fundamental change in the reality of the crisis. Even after the fall of the defunct regime, the role of the League continues to confront major challenges pertaining to the complexity of the transitional phase, the multiplicity of actors, and the persistence of foreign influences.

FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

FINDINGS:

- The study demonstrated that the position of the Arab League was characterised by a gradual approach, as it commenced with caution and calls for reform, before evolving into more explicit stances in condemning violence and demanding a political solution.
- The League relied upon a set of peaceful mechanisms—such as mediation, political initiatives, and observer missions—yet these tools lacked elements of enforcement and binding force, which limited their efficacy.
- The Syrian crisis revealed the limited capacity of the Arab League to independently manage the internal conflicts of Member States, a matter which prompted it to transfer the file to the United Nations.
- Divisions among Arab States played a pivotal role in weakening the collective stance and adversely affected the League's capacity to adopt decisive resolutions.
- The League contributed to keeping the Syrian issue within the sphere of regional and international attention, and helped break the political isolation at later stages, without this being translated into actual progress in the course of settlement.
- The study indicated that the phase following the fall of the regime opened the way for a renewed Arab role; however, it continues to confront challenges linked to the complexity of the transitional phase and the multiplicity of actors.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- The necessity of undertaking structural reforms in the Charter of the League of Arab States in a manner that enhances the efficacy of its resolutions and endows them with a more binding character, particularly Article 5 of the Charter. This Article should be expanded in tandem with Article 33 of the Charter of the United Nations, so that the means of peaceful settlement are set out clearly and precisely.
- Developing early and preventive intervention mechanisms, thereby enabling the League to address crises and conflicts in their initial stages before they exacerbate and transform into complex conflicts.
- Enhancing the role of the Arab Peace and Security Council and granting it broader powers in the field of conflict management, including follow-up and implementation.
- Working to mitigate the intensity of divisions among Member States by building Arab consensus based on mutual interests, in a manner that supports the unity of Arab decision-making.
- Activating the tools of diplomatic and economic leverage more effectively, and linking political initiatives to clear and time-bound implementation mechanisms.
- Strengthening coordination with international organisations, particularly the United Nations, while safeguarding the independence of Arab decision-making and its leading role in managing regional crises.

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